

Changing Trends in Quality Work-Life of IT Employees in the New Normal Era

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ABSTRACT

The concept of Quality Work-Life (QWL) refers to the extent to which an employee can meet significant personal needs because of their employment-related experiences. It is the total quality of an employee's work-life at an organization. The concept of work-life and work environment has completely changed for the employees in the Information Technology (IT) industry who have switched to working remotely or what is commonly known as "Work from home". The study aims to review various research conducted on different aspects of Quality Work-life among IT sector employees during the COVID-19 pandemic. In many different industries, the quality of the work-life is important since it affects employee happiness and organizational effectiveness. The extension of excellent employment opportunities and working conditions for employees is crucial for the organization's financial health.

The purpose of this study is to know the various attributes of Quality of Work-life (QoWL) of IT employees, and recent trends and approaches undertaken by IT organizations. The study also analyses the current QWL trends of IT employees and discusses opportunities available to improve the QoWL of IT employees. The research paper is based on primary data collected through a short survey circulated among IT employees and secondary data sourced from relevant literature from Academia and Google scholar databases and blogs.

Keywords: IT employees, Quality of Work-life, Work from home, New normal era.

1. INTRODUCTION

The term QWL describes how well an individual can meet important personal needs as a result of events related to their job. It covers aspects of work like job happiness, motivation, autonomy at work, productivity, occupational healthcare, safety and wellbeing, proper working hours, job security, suitable compensation, and its significance in the life of the employee.

Any organization's performance mostly depends on the caliber of its human resources. For businesses to continue to draw in and keep brilliant workers, a high degree of QWL is required. Organizations today operate in a competitive market with rapid technology advancements, which has a significant impact on

employment possibilities, the need for trained workers, management strategies, management policies, and management approaches. [1], [2]

Following the global spread of the COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020, it has altered how people live, think, and how businesses and organizations conduct their business. Work-from-home policies are one of the most obvious shifts in a variety of occupations. Although the idea is not entirely novel, the pandemic has forced a necessity and an unavoidable adjustment. This describes a flexible working style that is unrestricted by location, time, or the type of technical communication being used. It is predicted that this existing global job standard would endure even after the pandemic. This also affects how involved they are in their families, jobs, and other activities. The employee's QWL can be impacted by this. On the other hand, the IT workforce is one of those that is expanding the fastest in the current work climate. Greater work responsibilities and job satisfaction can be further increased by ensuring a balance between work, personal, and social life. [3], [4]

It is important to access the QWL of IT employees in the new normal era after the onset of the COVID - 19 pandemic, which has changed the way of working in the IT industry. The current trend in the IT sector includes remote work setup along with the existing work culture and system in the IT industry. The purpose of the study is to identify and describe the attributes of QWL in the current scenario of the IT sector, as well as to know the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the QWL in IT sector and suggest suitable solutions to improve QWL of IT industry.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Table 1: Some of the publications related to the QWL of IT employees

Sl. No.	Field of Research	Focus	References
1	Definition of QWL	QWL of an employee is defined and its importance in the competitive business world is discussed	[1], [2]
2	QWL of IT employees during the COVID-19 pandemic	Current trends in QWL of an IT employee are discussed. The study reveals the Work from Home (WFH) and its impact on the QWL of an IT employee.	[3], [4]
3	Attributes of QWL of an IT employee in the new normal era	The studies reveal various aspects of the QWL of an IT employee during the current scenario. Job security, fair compensation, job satisfaction, health, safety and wellbeing, productivity and motivation, Appropriate working hours, work autonomy, job stress, remote working, and its resources, training, and career prospects were discussed	[5] – [9]
4	Pros and Cons of current trends in QWL of an IT employee	The articles revealed the pros and cons of current trends in QWL of an IT employee, especially focusing on the WFH concept.	[10] – [13]
5	Suggestions to improve QWL	The study revealed suggestions to improve the QWL of an IT employee in the current scenario. Suggestions like setting the boundary between work and personal life, hybrid working mode, etc. were discussed.	[14] – [15]

Only a little amount of research has been done on the QWL of IT personnel in the new normal era and how the line is drawn between their job and personal lives when they work remotely. This study will lay the groundwork for future research to enhance the QWL of IT workers.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the research are as follows:

1. Identify and describe the attributes of QWL among the IT employees in the new normal era
2. ABCD analysis of current QWL trends in the IT sector
3. Suggest opportunities to improve QWL of IT employees

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on previous literature on QWL of IT employees and primarily focused on scholarly publications between 2020 to 2022 during the new normal era. The secondary data are taken from books, journals, and other reports that have been published in academia, blogs, and Google Scholar. The search was conducted using the terms "Quality Work-Life," "IT personnel," and "Work from Home." The articles were manually extracted, and based on the results, characteristics affecting IT employees' quality of life (QWL) were identified. Primary data was collected by distributing a short online survey through the survey FormApp application among IT employees of Morgan gate area of Mangalore, Karnataka, which consists of about 60 IT employees. A convenience sampling technique was used to facilitate sample selection. The survey was kept open for 3 days from 19th August to 21st August 2022, by posting the survey link on social media sites. 23 employees participated in the survey. The results from both primary and secondary data were subsequently examined using the ABCD management paradigm.

5. ATTRIBUTES OF QWL OF IT EMPLOYEES IN THE NEW NORMAL ERA

The QWL approach allows employees at all levels to influence the environment, processes, and results of their organizations effectively and actively. Its objective is to increase organizational effectiveness and improved employee quality of life at work. To maximize the advantages of enhancing the human component, QWL involves the efforts to establish integration among the technological, human, organizational, and societal demands. It is concerned with the general atmosphere at work, how work affects people and the efficiency of the organization. The main goal is to alter the workplace environment, which will eventually increase QWL and contribute to a higher standard of living across society.

The term "quality of work-life" refers to a person's perceptions of all aspects of employment, including financial compensation and benefits, job security, working conditions, interpersonal and organizational relationships, and the intrinsic value of the work in the person's life. [5], [6]

Fig 1: Attributes of QWL of IT employees

Attributes of QWL that impact IT employees in the current scenario are as follows:

- a) **Fair Compensation & Job Security:** Financial compensation should be given to the employees in line with their performance, knowledge, experience, and skills. If an employee's pay is not closely related to how well they do, it may cause them to be less productive and to be more dissatisfied with their jobs. Job security offered to staff in the form of long-term employment also enhances QWL.
- b) **Job Satisfaction:** It refers to an employee's level of satisfaction with their company. An employee's level of job satisfaction is influenced by several things. When an employer looks out for their employees' best interests, it increases job satisfaction, which boosts productivity. Higher job satisfaction is the result of a better quality of work-life since it improves the atmosphere of the job and the workplace. It raises an employee's overall effectiveness and efficiency while lowering absenteeism and turnover intentions. [7]
- c) **Occupational healthcare, safety, and well-being:** Safe working environment provides the basis for people to enjoy their work. The work should not pose hazards for the employees. Employees must have access to a good healthcare system. The company should involve in having more employee well-being programs.
- d) **Motivation:** The ability to act because one is motivated to do so is known as motivation. When employees are motivated, they make wise decisions and make good choices.
- e) **Productivity:** Productivity is referred to as the ratio of output to input. Employee productivity is influenced by job engagement, job satisfaction, and competency. The amount of these characteristics tend to be high when it comes to employee productivity. It typically falls in the alternative situation.
- f) **Appropriate time:** Working hours are the time a person devotes to doing an office job. A healthy balance between productivity, happiness and a decent quality of work life can be achieved with the right working hours.
- g) **Immediate supervisor and autonomy at work:** The immediate supervisor should promote employee participation and involvement, which helps them feel like a part of the company and fosters a sense of belonging. The decision-making process must involve the workers. They provide managers with

fresh, original thoughts and proposals, which helps to improve the workplace culture and atmosphere overall and raises employees' quality of work-life (QWL). The recognition at work encourages them to perform better.

- h) Nature of job and level of stress: If the nature of the job is such that it offers recognition, growth, creativity, and prospects for promotion, then it leads to improvement in QWL

A person's productivity and efficiency at work will suffer if they are under a lot of stress at work, which will lower their QWL. For employees to contribute effectively to the organization's goals, a company must create a stress-free work environment.

- i) Training and career prospects: Training and career advancement refer to appropriate training and opportunities for professional development and promotion. A successful employee should be rewarded with opportunities for advancement. With the new work setting, Work from Home, Appropriate resources and training must be provided to the employees to work remotely. Online workshops and certification courses can be a great opportunity for both employees for career advancement and for the organization to increase its talent pool. [8]

- j) Remote work, resources, and setting boundaries: Remote working is working away from an office setting where employees can do their office work from home or any other location. It gives employees flexibility and avoids commuting to the workplace.

Resources: Adequate support for work from home should be provided by the company which involves work setup like a laptop, desk, and chair, stable internet connection, and necessary software and IT support for remote functioning. Appropriate training must be provided to the employees. The organization and employees must set boundaries between the employee's work and personal life. Overwork can negatively affect both work and personal life. [9]

6. DISCUSSION

6.1: Primary data

A short survey was circulated among IT employees of Morgan gate, Mangalore locality via survey form application. 23 IT employees participated in the survey. They were requested to answer questions related to their personal experiences on QWL in the current scenario. They expressed the pros and cons of the current trends of QWL of IT employees.

Pros:

- No commuting to the workplace. The travel time can be utilized efficiently for personal work and with family. The money associated with traveling like fuel expenses or public transport can be saved. Office-related expenses like hotel food and expense on office clothes are saved. The employees can enjoy healthy home food and can work from the comfort of home or any tourist location. More time socializing with family and friends has improved personal relationships.
- Flexible working hours
- Better work-life balance and quality time spent on work and family
- More autonomy at work and no office distraction.
- New technology has brought in more opportunities and the employees can work with colleagues across the globe. Talents can be sourced from a remote location as there is no location constraint.
- Freelance work and jobs beyond boundaries are now possible. It is useful, especially for working women, and new mothers who can manage work and home life better. Attrition control
- Productivity has increased.
- Time can be utilized for upskilling and doing online courses.

Cons:

- Need to keep yourself constantly updated till retirement. Fear of losing the job to younger colleagues. Job saturation.
- Lack of socializing at work. It can cause hindrance to professional growth as interpersonal relations with peers and management might need more face-to-face time invested. Relations at work have become mundane and purely related to work topics.
- The learning process for freshers has decreased and too much lead time is needed to bring them to the production stage. Less learning opportunities onsite.
- Unable to monitor subordinates. No accountability. Too many loopholes, where people can escape from doing work.
- Depression due to isolation, and health issues. It is a lazy job with fewer physical movements.
- Reservation at jobs is a serious concern that can affect the jobs of talented employees from getting jobs.
- Extended working hours. No clear boundaries between work and personal life, negatively affecting both. It can cause reduced work-life balance, less productivity, and burnout. Unrealistic deadlines and expected work sometimes on holidays and weekends.
- Can take a long time to solve issues, which could have been solved in less time when working at the office. No, IT supports
- It develops lots of introverts.
- Leads to procrastination.
- Office set-up cost. Network issues. Network security and the threat of information leakage due to the use of a personal computer.
- Disturbance from family members, children, and noisy neighbors.
- Sales related to medical and product sales and customers can be less productive.
- The economy of the transport and hotel industry is negatively affected.

6.2: Secondary data:

The following pros and cons were extracted from previous studies:

Pros:

The employment trends in the IT sector now promote a diversified workforce, reduced investment, a new way of working, and organizational profits. It has a positive impact on the company's earnings, is cost-effective, less time-consuming, flexible, enabled optimum resource utilization, provided higher return from less cost, saves commute time, allows for flex time, empowers employees, reduces staff costs, reduces costs for maintaining office space, increases employment, strengthens employee-employer relations, and benefits many stakeholders. It is environmentally friendly, relatively risk-free, draws employees, improves work quality, increases efficiency, produces results quickly, gives workers access to the newest technologies, lowers absenteeism, reduces pollution, eases traffic congestion, improves living conditions, and encourages a greener environment.

Cons:

Current IT employment offers advantages and disadvantages, much like a coin with two sides. The tendency to work long hours, the inability to collaborate with coworkers, the tendency for higher work intensity, the challenges of setting up and running technology, the inability to access timely information,

the challenges of time management, and the negative effects on subjective well-being, the reduced social contact that results in loneliness, the deterioration of self-esteem & motivation are all effects of remote working. These undesirable results usually affect the stakeholders in short term. It can cause employee health problems, which lead to increased work intensity, and may exacerbate already-existing labor market disparities. They may also make it difficult to distinguish between work and personal obligations, cause too many distractions, including children, and reduce the visibility of fairness in performance reviews. [10] – [13]

7. ABCD ANALYSIS OF QWL TRENDS IN THE IT SECTOR

A model framework called Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages (ABCD) is used to evaluate a model plan's effectiveness in any firm. Using the ABCD analytical methodology, we examine QWL trends of IT employees in this article using primary data from focus group discussions and secondary data from previous studies. This analysis can assist in developing appropriate strategies for the seamless transition to the new normal and will help to understand the limitations of the IT sector.

Table 2: ABCD analysis of the current QWL trends among IT employees

Advantages	Constraints
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No commuting to the workplace and no need to deal with traffic. • More flexible working hours • Better work-life balance • Greater productivity and cost savings • Good pay packages • No office distraction • Reduced absenteeism and turnover intentions • Attrition control • More autonomy at work • Can deal with multiple customers at a time and no need to physically meet them. • Customers can buy the products and services online. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less visibility on fairness in a performance review. • No accountability • Data theft and miscommunication can occur • Health issues • Reservation in jobs can lead to the loss of jobs for talented human resources. • Home office set up cost and network issues. • Reduced motivation and self-esteem. Develops introverts. • Depression due to isolation • Medical and other product sales may not be productive. We may lose customers that prefer face-to-face sales meetings. • Lack of next-layer leadership • Leads to procrastination
Benefits	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New technology can bring in more opportunities • Increased job opportunities and freelance work • Talent can be sourced from remote locations as there is no location constraint. • Can interact with colleagues and clients across the globe easily. • Time saved due to no travel can be utilized to spend time with family and recreational activities. • Higher organizational commitment • Able to look after dependents at home • Save money on travel, food, and office-related expenses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overwork due to extended working hours can lead to burnout and work-life imbalance. Can negatively affect the well-being of the employees • Difficulty to collaborate with colleagues. No, IT supports. • Inability to access time resources that can be better done at the office. • Network issues • Need to be up to date constantly and higher competition. • Less opportunity to socialize with peers and management and learn new things. • Lack of sufficient monitoring system of working hours, progress on the job, and lack of

	supervision. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distraction from family members and household chores and noisy neighborhood
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8. RECOMMENDATIONS TO IMPROVE QWL OF IT EMPLOYEES

A few steps can be taken to improve the QWL of the IT Employees:

- A hybrid mode of working, which is a combination of work from home and work from the office should be introduced. This will help IT employees choose between the 2 modes of working or a combination of modes of work. [14]
- Strict working hours restriction policy
- Set up work and personal life boundaries
- Adequate training and workshop should be provided to the employees to keep them updated on the current technology
- Sufficient resources/allowances to buy resources should be provided by the company to have work set up at home.
- Since the pandemic has reduced or people have come to terms with the new normal situation, regular colleague meetups, and recreational activities must be conducted by the office to increase the team spirit between colleagues.
- Few meetings which need face-to-face working can be shifted to work from the office instead of working from home.
- The company should have good health insurance coverage for employee and their family members.
- Employees should spend time keeping healthy and fit by engaging in physical exercises.
- Reservation in jobs must be abolished to give equal opportunity to talent.

9. CONCLUSION

The study was conducted through a review of literature collected as secondary data from various journals, newsletters, and blogs. The study initially focused on seeking the attributes of Quality work-life of an IT employee in the current scenario. Later data was collected by both primary and secondary data to deduce the ABCD framework of QWL of an IT employee. Primary data was collected via a short survey consisting of open-end questions related to the pros and cons of quality work life among IT employees. An employee who is content and in excellent health will always have a lower turnover rate, make wise decisions, and help the company achieve its objectives. Guaranteed high quality of work-life will not only draw in young, fresh talent but also keep hold of veteran talent. The study revealed the QoWL of the IT employees had its share of ups and downs during the pandemic. Some of the causes for increased QWL are flexible work hours, no travel time and hence less money spent on office and travel, more time spent with family, no location constraints, and some of the causes of reduced QWL are increased working hours and no boundaries between work and personal life, no socializing with colleagues, depression due to isolation, etc. When an employee is happy with his/ her work, productivity and performance will increase. The study concluded with suitable suggestions to improve the QWL of IT employees in the current scenario.

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